

'Quantus tremor est futurus': Nebra's Terrifying Last Judgement

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Abstract

José de Nebra (1702–68) composed his *Missa pro defunctis* ostensibly for the funeral of the Queen of Spain, Maria Barbara Braganza, in 1758, although it must already have been complete at the time of her death. The work presents an interesting mix of styles ranging from Renaissance polyphony to *galant* passages, but the movement which stands out is undoubtedly the *Dies irae*. Drawing on his theatrical experience, Nebra provided music which would have created a strong emotional impact within the context of a solemn funeral rite. In particular, he made widespread use of the *tempesta* topic, introducing disruptive musical elements not normally associated with liturgical music at the time. There are also *ombra* references, again designed to unsettle the audience. This paper explores Nebra's setting of the *Dies irae* in detail, identifying the array of musical signifiers involved, and demonstrating that he had achieved a mastery of *tempesta* that pre-dates more celebrated examples by Gluck, Mozart and Haydn.¹

The year 1758 saw the publication of one of the most influential books on aesthetics during the 19th century, Edmund Burke's *A Philosophical Enquiry into the Origins of Our Ideas of the Sublime and Beautiful*. In it, Burke focuses much attention on the sources of sublime emotion, in particular the 'Sublime of Terror':²

Whatever is fitted in any sort to excite the ideas of pain, and danger, that is to say, whatever is in any sort terrible, or is conversant about terrible objects, or operates in a manner analogous to terror, is a source of the *sublime*; that is, it is productive of the strongest emotion which the mind is capable of feeling.

¹ A version of this paper was given at the *Congreso Internacional "Tópicos en la música hispana: siglos XVIII-XXI"* at the University of Valladolid, 20–22 Oct 2022. Since the conference was about the application of topic theory to a range of Spanish music, the focus of the paper is very much on musical signification as exhibited in the chosen piece, rather than on the historical context of funerary music in 18th-century Spain. I am grateful to the reviewer for suggestions of sources that may be of interest to the reader who wishes to explore the background more fully.

² Edmund Burke, *A Philosophical Enquiry into the Origins of Our Ideas of the Sublime and Beautiful* (London: J. Dodsley, 1757). Repr. edited by J. T. Boulton (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1958), 39. Burke's thoughts need to be considered within the wider development of writings on sources of the sublime throughout the 19th century. See Peter Le Huray and James Day, eds., *Music and Aesthetics in the Eighteenth and Early Nineteenth Centuries* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1981), 4–6. A more detailed study is Samuel H. Monk, *The Sublime: A Study of Critical Theories in Eighteenth-Century England* (New York: Modern Language Association of America, 1935). A valuable collection of source readings is by ed. A. Ashfield and P. de Bolla, *The Sublime: A Reader in British Eighteenth-Century Aesthetic Theory* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996).

In 18th-century music, this emotion is most clearly expressed through the *tempesta* topic, a term applied to music that exhibits agitated or violent characteristics in order to evoke terror and chaos.³ Features of the style include fast tempo, rapid scale passages, driving rhythmic figurations, strong accents, full textures, and robust instrumentation including prominent brass and timpani. Examples of musical storm depictions stretch right back to the operas of the early eighteenth century, where audiences could experience spectacular stage effects (including sound effects provided by wind machines and thunder sheets) as well as powerful music, for a true assault on the senses. Storm scenes were especially popular in the operas of the French court at the beginning of the eighteenth century, where the plots frequently allowed opportunities for divine intervention. This association between storms and the supernatural is of central importance. The Age of Reason could well offer sound scientific reasons to explain extreme weather conditions, but superstitions persisted, and storms still offered a very real sense of danger to anyone unfortunate enough to be caught in one.

Composers soon came to realise that, in order to write more effective storm music, they would need to find ways not just to represent the storm, but to convey that sense of danger to the audience. This was a gradual process, and it is difficult to pinpoint when this transition took place, but it seems clear that at the start of the eighteenth century the emphasis was on representing the storm through simple tone-painting, but by the end of it there was a clear intention on the part of composers to provoke feelings of terror in audiences.

The label *Sturm und Drang* (especially in relation to Haydn's symphonies of the late 1760s and early 1770s) is demonstrably unsatisfactory as an accurate identifier of such music. The stylistic origins clearly lie much earlier than the German literary movement of that name, deriving from storm scenes (including floods, earthquakes, and conflagrations) in early eighteenth-century operas, and a supernatural association is evident because these scenes are invariably instigated, and often quelled, by irate deities. My substituting the term with *tempesta* avoids this misleading association. Composers and publishers of concertos and symphonies in the eighteenth century frequently used the word as a descriptive label for storm depictions (with works or individual movements headed *La tempesta*), and the term *aria di tempesta* for operatic arias of a stormy nature was widely recognised. The Italianate word reflects this tradition, and is intended to complement *ombra* (the style employed for the appearance of ghosts, witches, oracles etc.) because the two have associations with the supernatural, and they share many characteristics.⁴ A summary of the musical features associated with these topics is given in Table 1.⁵

³See Clive McClelland, *Tempesta: Stormy Music in the Eighteenth Century* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2017).

⁴See Clive McClelland, *Ombra: Supernatural Music in the Eighteenth Century* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2012).

⁵Adapted from the table given in Clive McClelland 'Ombra and Tempesta' in ed. Danuta Mirka, *The Oxford Handbook of Topic Theory* (Oxford: OUP, 2014), 279–300.

Table 1: A comparison of *ombra* and *tempesta* characteristics

	<i>Ombra</i>	<i>Tempesta</i>
General	'high' style, sombre, sustained	agitated, declamatory, stormy
Tempo	slow or moderate	fast
Tonality	flat keys (especially minor keys) occasionally remote, shifting, unusual modulations	mainly minor keys, especially D minor, shifting, unusual modulations
Harmony	'surprise' progressions, bold, chromatic - especially diminished 7ths	'surprise' progressions, bold, chromatic, frequently on the dominant
Melody	exclamatory, often fragmented, sometimes augmented/diminished leaps, occasionally narrow intervals contrasting with wide leaps, monotones/triadic lines for oracles and invocations	disjunct motion, often fragmented, with very wide leaps, sometimes augmented or diminished leaps
Bass	chromatic stepwise movement, descending tetrachord, sometimes augmented or diminished leaps, repeated notes, pedals, ostinato	occasionally chromatic, sometimes augmented or diminished leaps, repeated notes (<i>Trommelbass</i>), pedals, ostinato
Figuration	motivic repetition (including 'sigh' motifs), tremolo effects, sometimes rising and falling scales	rapid scale passages, tremolo effects, repeated notes, <i>tirades</i>
Rhythm	restless motion, syncopation, majestic or ponderous dotted rhythms, sometimes dactyls/ <i>versi</i> <i>sdrucchioli</i> , pauses	restless motion, driving forward, syncopation, irregular rhythms, sometimes pauses
Texture	sudden contrasts, often dense, sometimes lines doubled in octaves, rarely imitative	full textures, but often lines doubled in octaves, sometimes imitative or sequential
Dynamics	strong contrasts, sudden outbursts, crescendo effects, unexpected silence	mostly loud, strong accents, crescendo effects
Instrumentation	unusual, low tessitura, dark timbre, especially trombones	prominent string writing, full scoring often involving brass and timpani

The features of both topics represent aspects of music that might be disturbing to the listener, particularly one in the eighteenth century. It should be emphasized, however, that in isolation, one of these effects would have had little impact. It is when several occur in combination that the effect is more powerful. Audiences would have been well used to such writing from theatrical scenes involving the supernatural, such as hell scenes, pronouncements by deities, incantations, ghosts etc., and especially storms, which are invariably inspired by irate

gods, and therefore associated with the supernatural. The important difference between these two topics is that the slower tempo of *ombra* gives rise to feelings of awe and horror, while the faster and more frenzied *tempesta* inspires panic and terror.

Ombra as a topic is not uncommon in eighteenth-century sacred music, since generating a sense of awe is sometimes appropriate (e.g. in Old Testament accounts that form the basis of many oratorios). *Tempesta*, originally employed for storms in the theatre, also began to find its way into other kinds of music. This included programmatic orchestral music, and even absolute music (of which Haydn's so-called *Sturm und Drang* symphonies are the most celebrated examples). With sacred music, texts that dealt with storms and other terrifying events such as earthquakes and damnation gave rise to appropriately frightening music, although in a church context there were naturally some constraints on excess. Of particular interest in this respect is the text of the 'Dies Irae' in settings of the Requiem Mass, with its powerful references to the events of the Last Judgement.

This brings us to the grand setting of the *Missa pro defunctis* by José de Nebra of 1758 (coincidentally the same year as Burke's publication).⁶ It was first performed at the funeral of Maria Barbara of Braganza, the Queen of Spain and wife of Ferdinand VI. She was an enthusiastic patron of the arts, and she had employed Domenico Scarlatti as Master of Music until his death in the previous year. She had also appointed Farinelli as director of the court opera, so there was a clear desire to bring the music at court up to date with the latest Italian developments. Nebra himself had made his name in the early part of his career as a composer of operas and *zarzuelas* (over 70 in all), but following his appointment as organist to the Royal Chapel in 1736, sacred music became an important part of his output. It appears likely that Nebra's Requiem was composed some time before the funeral took place, as it would have been impossible for him to have completed a work of such a scale within the short time between the Queen's death and funeral. A revised version of the Requiem was used for the obsequies of Ferdinand VI the following year, and it continued to be performed at royal funerals into the next century.⁷

Nebra's Requiem is by no means conventional, but the music is predominantly calm without being overly gloomy. There are no set-piece arias, the emphasis being on choral contrapuntal textures (with some solo passages interjected).⁸ These are rooted in Renaissance practices, even to the extent that *cantus firmus* based on plainsong chants is occasionally employed. There are some interesting sequential modulations and one or two nice touches of orchestral colour, but the overall mood is one of appropriate solemnity. His setting of the *Dies irae* provides a marked contrast to all this. The terrors of the Last Judgement are vividly evoked, being conveyed with considerable relish. The text in the opening verses of the *Dies irae* provides plenty of powerful imagery for a composer to explore in their music (see Table 2).⁹

⁶This is not to say that Nebra was directly influenced by Burke's writing, but ideas about the sublime were certainly in circulation throughout Europe (see above, n.1). For a survey of Nebra's output, see M Salud Álvarez Martínez: 'José de Nebra a la luz de las últimas investigaciones', *Anuario Musical Barcelona* Vol. 47, (Jan 1, 1992): 153-73.

⁷It was also performed once a year for All Soul's Day (November 2nd).

⁸The vocal forces are divided into two groups, comprising a four-part solo group (Choir 1) and a standard SATB chorus (Choir 2).

⁹https://cpdl.org/wiki/index.php/dies%20irae#Text_and_translations [accessed 12.3.25]

Table 2: *Dies irae* verses 1–8 text and translation

1. Dies irae, dies illa solvet saeculum in favilla, teste David cum Sibylla.	1. A day of wrath; that day, it will dissolve the world into glowing ashes, as attested by David together with the Sibyl.
2. Quantus tremor est futurus, quando iudex est venturus, cuncta stricte discussurus?	2. What trembling will there be, when the Judge shall come to examine everything in strict justice.
3. Tuba mirum spargens sonum, per sepulchra regionum, coget omnes ante thronum.	3. The trumpet's wondrous call sounding abroad in tombs throughout the world shall drive everybody forward to the throne.
4. Mors stupebit et natura, cum resurget creatura, iudicanti responsura.	4. Death and nature shall stand amazed when creation rises again to give answer to its Judge.
5. Liber scriptus proferetur in quo totum continetur, unde mundus iudicetur.	5. A written book will be brought forth in which everything is contained from which the world shall be judged.
6. Iudex ergo cum sedebit, quidquid latet, apparebit; nil inultum remanebit.	6. So when the Judge is seated, whatever is hidden will be made known: nothing shall go unpunished.
7. Quid sum miser tunc dicturus? Quem patronum rogaturus, cum vix iustus sit securus?	7. What shall I, wretch, say at that time? What advocate shall I entreat (to plead for me) when scarcely the righteous shall be safe from damnation?
8. Rex tremendae maiestatis, qui salvandos salvas gratis, salva me, fons pietatis.	8. King of awesome majesty, who to grants salvation to those that are to be saved, save me, o fount of Piety.

Interestingly, Nebra does not set verses 5–7, where the ideas expressed are rather less impactful.¹⁰ Instead the focus is on the first four verses, depicting the final cataclysm and the awe-inspiring moment of damnation or redemption. This imagery continues in verse 8. Each of the remaining five verses is treated by Nebra as a discrete unit, with a clear musical theme (or group of themes), followed either by sequential development or a codetta, or sometimes both. The structure is summarised in Table 3, along with a summary of the main keys and the musical topics employed.

¹⁰This may have been because these verses were not a prescribed part of the liturgy at the Spanish royal court. 'Confutatis maledictis', with its portrayal of the flames of hell, is also not set. The supplicatory tone of the final verse, 'Lacrymosa', gives rise here to a separate movement.

Table 3: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* structure, tonality and topics

Bar	Text	Theme	Key	Topics
	<u>Introduction</u>			
1		1	d	<i>tempesta</i>
8		2	d	<i>tempesta</i>
12		3	d	<i>tempesta</i>
	<u>Verse 1</u>			
19	<i>Dies irae</i>	1 & 2	d	<i>tempesta</i>
30	<i>Dies illa</i>	mod seq	Bb	
41	<i>Solvete saeculum</i>	mod seq	g	
52	<i>Teste David</i>	codetta	d	
	<u>Verse 2</u>			
65	<i>Quantus tremor</i>	4	Bb - Eb	<i>tempesta</i>
74	<i>Quando judex</i>	mod seq	F	
78	<i>Cuncta stricte</i>	mod seq	g	
	<u>Verse 3</u>			
87	<i>Tuba mirum</i>	2	F	fanfare/ <i>tempesta</i>
97	<i>Per sepulcrum</i>	5	F/f	<i>ombra</i>
112	<i>Coget omnes</i>	codetta	F	
	<u>Verse 4</u>			
122	<i>Mors stupebit</i>	6	a - C	<i>ombra</i>
133	<i>Cum resurget</i>	6, (3)	d - a	<i>ombra</i> , then <i>tempesta</i>
141	<i>Judicanti</i>	codetta	a - d - a	
	<u>Verse 5*</u>			
157	<i>Rex tremendae</i>	1 & 2	F	<i>tempesta</i>
168	<i>Rex tremendae</i>	mod seq	d	
179	<i>Qui salvandos</i>	7	g	Learned/ <i>Empfindsamkeit</i>
184	<i>Salva me</i>	codetta	d	
201	<i>Salva me</i>	coda	d	

*Verse 8 of the original text, verses 5–7 being omitted.

There are seven identifiable thematic components. Some of these themes return at later stages, with the first two coming back at the start of the final verse ('Rex tremendae') to create a rounding out of the overall form. The choice of the home key of D minor is significant, since it is widely used for supernatural storm scenes in opera, and a high proportion of both *ombra* and *tempesta* references in the latter half of the eighteenth century are in that key.¹¹

¹¹ Flat minor keys are especially prominent in Requiem settings from around 1750 onwards, especially D minor and C minor. See McClelland, *Ombra*, 191–2. For more on settings of the *Dies irae*, see McClelland, *Tempesta*, 163–6. For the significance of flat minor keys, see Rita Steblin, *A History of Key Characteristics in the Eighteenth and Early Nineteenth Centuries* (Ann Arbor: UMI Research Press, 1983). While Nebra's handling of tonality is undoubtedly influenced by the traditional church modes, they clearly map onto the standardised tonal system established during

Here, Nebra employs a bold tonal scheme that unexpectedly encompasses keys more remote from D minor, so while the usual tonic, dominant and relative major keys appear, there are excursions into other keys, such as B flat, E flat and C majors, and a passing inflection towards F minor. Such fluctuations in tonality serve to add to the unsettling effect of the music. In terms of topical references, *tempesta* is the principal one. Nebra also employs *ombra*, learned style, *Emfindsamkeit* and fanfare topics, all examples of a high style appropriate for the solemnity of the occasion.

The lively introduction presents three themes, exhibiting powerful *tempesta* characteristics (see Example 1).¹² The first theme (bars 1–8) consists of repeated figurations, fast arpeggios, a crescendo and an insistent *Trommelbass* that drives the music forward. Meanwhile the flutes play a descending tonic arpeggio in semibreves, prefiguring the rising arpeggio that the chorus is about to sing. The second theme (bars 8–12) is stated in bare octaves, and contains a syncopated figure and a prominent dotted motif, as well as more arpeggios. Alternating bars of contrasting dynamics add to the chaotic effect. The rapid rising and falling scales (from halfway through bar 12) characterise the third theme. All of these features contribute to a strong *tempesta* reference, and together they provide a lot of the thematic material that appears subsequently.

Themes 1 and 2 are immediately taken up by the chorus (the arpeggio in semibreves now rising), but are not straightforwardly repeated, since further *tempesta* features are added, namely sudden accents and strong contrasts in texture. This material is then spun out through B flat major and G minor with modulating sequences and the verse ends with a brief codetta in D minor. Verse 2 (bars 65–86) opens with a new idea (Theme 4), in which alternating notes are a prominent feature (evidently an effect inspired by the word ‘tremor’), along with juxtaposed dynamic contrasts and a descending chromatic line, more features that are associated with *tempesta* (see Example 2).

From bar 72 this passage is then repeated a tone higher, which serves to add to the tension. Verse 3 (bars 87–121) starts out with a return of Theme 2 (bar 8), now in F major and with additional dotted notes that lend a fanfare-like quality, enhanced by the echo effects.

At bar 97, a new texture is introduced (Theme 5), involving a solo chant-like monotone and tonic minor inflections as well as alternations between *forte* and *piano* dynamics and a stepwise descending bass line. Although the tempo has not been altered, the long note-values create a much slower feel, suggesting the *ombra* topic, entirely fitting for the sepulchral imagery of the text (see Example 3).¹³

A new idea (Theme 6) is introduced at the start of Verse 4, but the *ombra* atmosphere is maintained by the fragmented lines, pauses, slow syncopations and the unusual string textures (including use of *pizzicato*) that vividly depict death itself frozen in a state of astonishment, precisely the emotional response an *ombra* reference is designed to achieve (see Example 4).

the eighteenth century.

¹²I am most grateful to Zachary Kleinhous for permission to use his new performing edition of the score, a project which was made possible with funding from the Instituto Cervantes. Also available is the critical edition by Luis Antonio González Marín: *José de Nebra: Oficio y Misa para las Reales Honras de la Reina D^a. María Bárbara, que goza de Dios*, (Madrid, Instituto Complutense de Ciencias Musicales, 2003).

¹³To the modern listener, this texture is reminiscent of the writing used for oracles, most notably in Mozart's *Idomeneo*, and later with the music for the Statue of the Commendatore in *Don Giovanni*. See McClelland, *Ombra*, 152–63.

A return to *tempesta* is then heralded by rapid quaver writing in a variant of Theme 3 from bar 138. Verse 5 sees a return to themes 1 and 2 (as stated by the chorus from bar 18), extended sequentially and leading to one final new idea, Theme 7, from bar 179 (see Example 5).

Here the focus of the text is on salvation, so the musical writing is very much in the idiom of ecclesiastical counterpoint, with suspensions and sighing figures predominating, a mixture of learned and *Empfindsamkeit* topics. The movement closes with repeated pleas for deliverance back in the home key of D minor.

It is difficult to know how a congregation at a grand funeral for a royal personage might have reacted to this. The Spanish court was a conservative one, even by the standards of the other courts of Europe. Nebra's use of such theatrical musical language (in which he was well versed) shows his willingness to manipulate the emotions of his audience despite the requirements of a solemn liturgical occasion. Nowadays we are used to vivid musical portrayals of the Last Judgement, but Nebra's setting pre-dates all of these. Eighteenth-century Spain is usually regarded as something of a backwater in terms of musical innovation, but Nebra was clearly ahead of his time. The fact that his Requiem remained as the number one choice for royal funerals for more than a century afterwards suggests that the 'Dies irae', far from causing offence, met with considerable approval, a quasi-operatic religious manifestation of the 'Sublime of Terror'.

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Example 1: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* bars 1–18 (Themes 1, 2 & 3)

Sequencia
Dies irae

José de Nebra

Allegro Vivo

[Flauta I]
[Flauta II]
[Violin I]
[Violin II]
[Viola]
[Acompañamiento]

[Fl. I]
[Fl. II]
[Vln. I]
[Vln. II]
[Vla.]
[Acomp.]

[Fl. I]
[Fl. II]
[Vln. I]
[Vln. II]
[Vla.]
[Acomp.]

Example 2: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* bars 63–72 (Theme 4)

63

[Ti. I] *f* byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, *solo* quan - tus tre - mor est fu - tu - rus, quan-do ju -

[Ti. II] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[C.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[T.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[Ti.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[C.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[T.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[B.] byl - la. *f* Quan-tus tre - mor, quan-do ju -

[Acomp.] *f* *p* *f*

Example 3: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* bars 63–72 (Theme 5)

93

[Ti. I] *solo* spar - gens so - num, spar-gens so-num per se - pul - cra re - gi - o - num,

[Ti. II] spar-gens so-num per

[C.] spar-gens so-num per

[T.] spar - gens so-num per

[Ti.] mi-rum spar-gens so-num per

[C.] mi-rum spar - gens so-num per

[T.] mi-rum spar-gens so-num per

[B.] mi-rum spar - gens so-num per

[Acomp.] *p* *f* *p* *f* *p* *f*

Example 4: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* bars 116–26 (Theme 6)

116

[Ti. I] num, an-te thro - num. Mors, *p tutto* mors, mors.

[Ti. II] num, an-te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[C.] num, an-te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[T.] num, an-te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[Ti.] num, co - get om - nes an - te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[C.] num, co - get om - nes an - te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[T.] num, co - get om - nes an - te thro - num. Mors, mors, mors, *p tutto*

[B.] num, co - get om - nes an - te thro - num. Mors *p tutto* stu-pe - bit, mors, *p tutto*

[Acomp.] Punteado

Example 5: Nebra, Requiem *Dies irae* bars 176–83 Theme 7

176

[Ti. I] ta - tis, ma - jes - ta - tis, qui sal - van - dos sal - vas gra - - -

[Ti. II] Rex tre - men-dæ ma - jes - ta - tis, qui sal - van - dos sal - vas, sal - vas gra -

[C.] Rex tre - men-dæ ma - jes - ta - tis, qui sal - van - dos sal - vas, sal - vas gra

[T.] ta - tis, ma - jes - ta - tis, qui sal - van - dos sal - vas gra -

[Ti.] dæ, Rex tre - men-dæ ma - jes - ta - tis,

[C.] - Rex tre men dæ ma jes ta tis,

[T.] dæ, Rex tre - men-dæ ma - jes - ta - tis,

[B.] dæ, Rex tre - men-dæ ma - jes - ta - tis,

[Acomp.]